

**SYNTHESIS OF POLYNUCLEAR HYDROCARBONS WITH FUSED
cyclopENTANE RING. PART V. cyclopENTENO-
FLUORANTHENE DERIVATIVES**

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The syntheses of several dialkyl- and diaryl-11:12-cyclopentenofluoranthenes have been carried out by the application of the Diels-Alder reaction.

A very convenient procedure for the synthesis of fluoranthene derivatives is that used by Dilthey by the application of the Diels-Alder reaction. He treated the cyclopentadienone derivative, accecyclone (I: R=R'=Ph), with maleic anhydride and other dienophiles when fluoranthene derivatives were formed by the loss of the carbonyl bridge of the adduct. 10:11:12:13-Tetraphenylfluoranthene had been synthesised starting from accecyclone and tolane (Dilthey, Heukels and Schäfer, *Ber.*, 1938, 71, 974). By an extension of this procedure Allen and Van Allan (*J. Org. Chem.*, 1952, 17, 845) have synthesised a large number of substituted fluoranthenes. We have in the present investigation utilised this method for the synthesis of a number of substituted 11:12-cyclopentenofluoranthenes (IV).

When accecyclone (I: R=R'=Ph) was taken as the diene component and Δ^1 -cyclopentene-1:2-dicarboxylic anhydride (II) as the dienophile, they readily formed an adduct from which the endocarbonyl bridge was eliminated at the temperature of the reaction that was carried out in boiling xylene solution. The decarbonylated adduct (III: R=R'=Ph), so obtained, was decarboxylated and dehydrogenated by distillation with soda-lime under slightly reduced pressure when 10:13-diphenyl-11:12-cyclopentenofluoranthene (IV: R=R'=Ph) was obtained.

In place of accecyclone, the dimers of 2:5-dialkylcyclopentadienones (I:R=R'=alkyl) had also been used. The dimer dissociated to the monomer (Allen and Van Allan, *loc. cit.*) and the latter then formed the adduct. By following this procedure 10:13-dimethyl-, 10:13-diethyl- and 10-methyl-13-ethyl-11:12-cyclopentenofluoranthenes (IV:R=R'=Me or Et and R=Me; R'=Et) had been synthesised starting respectively from the dimers of 2:5 dimethyl-, 2:5-diethyl- and 2-methyl-5-ethyl-3:4-(1':8'-naphthylene)-cyclopentadienone (I:R=R'=Me or Et, and R=Me; R'=Et) and the dienophile, Δ^1 -cyclopentene-1:2-dicarboxylic anhydride (II). These hydrocarbons are all light yellow substances.

2:5-Di-*p*-tolyl-3:4-(1':8'-naphthylene)-cyclopentadienone (I:R=R'=p-tol) and Δ^1 -cyclopentene-1:2-dicarboxylic anhydride (II) formed the adduct (III:R=R'=p-tol). This adduct has not been decarboxylated to the corresponding hydrocarbon.

EXPERIMENTAL

11:12-Dihydro-10:13-diphenyl-11:12-cyclopentenofluoranthene-11:12-dicarboxylic Anhydride (III:R=R'=Ph).—Accecyclone (I:R=R'=Ph) (Dilthey, ter Horst and Schommer, *J. prakt. Chem.*, 1935, 143, 189) (15 g.) and Δ^1 -cyclopentene-1:2-dicarboxylic anhydride (II; 8 g.) in dry xylene (40 c.c.) were refluxed in a glycerine bath at 150°-155° (bath temperature) until the evolution of carbon monoxide had ceased (about 6 hours). The reaction mixture was then cooled and allowed to stand. The separated product was filtered, washed with a little benzene and crystallised from a large volume of benzene, m.p. 269°, yield 9 g. (Found: C, 85.0; H, 4.4. $C_{33}H_{22}O_2$ requires C, 84.9; H, 4.7 per cent). Benzene-insoluble product (2 g.) was left. This was not a sharp melting substance and was evidently a polymerised product.

10:13-Diphenyl-11:12-cyclopentenofluoranthene (IV:R=R'=Ph).—The adduct (III:R=R'=Ph) (5 g.) was mixed with soda-lime (8 g.) and heated in a long Pyrex test tube under reduced pressure. A yellow sublimate (2 g.) with a green fluorescence condensed on the cooler end of the tube. The sublimate was purified by repeated crystallisation from hexane and obtained as stout pale yellow needles, m.p. 217-18°. (Found: C, 94.09; H, 5.9. $C_{31}H_{22}$ requires C, 94.41; H, 5.58 per cent).

11:12-Dihydro-10:13-dimethyl-11:12-cyclopentenofluoranthene-11:12-dicarboxylic Anhydride (III:R=R'=Me).—The dimer of 2:5-dimethyl-3:4-(1':8'-naphthylene)-cyclopentadienone (I:R=R'=Me) (10 g.) (Allen and Van Allan, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1952, 17, 852) and Δ^1 -cyclopentene-1:2-dicarboxylic anhydride (II; 7 g.) in xylene (30 c.c.) were heated as before until evolution of carbon monoxide had ceased (4 hours). The separated adduct crystallised from acetic anhydride or benzene in needles, m.p. 233°, yield 6 g. (Found: C, 80.35; H, 5.2. $C_{28}H_{18}O_2$ requires C, 80.7; H, 5.2 per cent).

10:13-Dimethyl-11:12-cyclopentenofluoranthene (IV:R=R'=Me).—The adduct (III:R=R'=Me) (6 g.) and soda-lime (8 g.) were heated under reduced pressure. A yellow sublimate (2.5 g.) was obtained. It was crystallised from hexane and melted unsharply at 165°. It was purified through the picrate, which was obtained as deep orange needles from absolute alcoholic solution, m.p. 203°-204°. The picrate dissociated on recrystallisation from alcohol. (Found: C, 64.6; H, 3.9. $C_{27}H_{21}O_7N_3$

requires C, 64.93; H, 4.2 per cent). The hydrocarbon was regenerated from the picrate and crystallised from alcohol in yellow flakes, m.p. 178°. (Found: C, 92.98; H, 6.99. $C_{21}H_{18}$ requires C, 93.33; H, 6.66 per cent).

The dimer of 2-methyl-5-ethyl-3:4-(1':8'-naphthylene)-cyclopentadienone (I:R=Me; R'=Et) was prepared exactly as in the case of the dimer of (I:R=R'=Me) (Allen and Van Allan, *loc. cit.*) starting from acenaphthenequinone and *n*-propylethyl ketone. The carbinol, first prepared from these two, crystallised from alcohol in needles, and was obtained as a mixture of isomers, m.p. 180-81°, sintering earlier. (Found: C, 81.7; H, 6.1. $C_{18}H_{16}O_2$ requires C, 81.81; H, 6.06 per cent). The dienone was obtained as dimer by dehydration of the carbinol in acetic anhydride solution with the addition of a few drops of H_2SO_4 (conc.). It crystallised from benzene, m.p. 190°, sintering earlier. (Found: C, 87.8; H, 6.0. $C_{18}H_{14}O$ requires C, 87.8; H, 5.7 per cent).

11:12-Dihydro-10-methyl-13-ethyl-11:12-cyclopenteno-fluoranthene-11:12-dicarboxylic Anhydride (III:R=Me; R'=Et).—The above dimer (I:R=Me; R'=Et) (12 g.) and Δ^1 -cyclopentene-1:2-dicarboxylic anhydride (8 g.) were heated in xylene solution, as described before. The adduct was crystallised from benzene, m.p. 174°, yield 6 g. It gave a pinkish fluorescence in benzene solution. (Found: C, 81.0; H, 5.8. $C_{24}H_{20}O_2$ requires C, 80.89; H, 5.61 per cent).

10-Methyl-13-ethyl-11:12-cyclopenteno-fluoranthene (IV:R=Me; R'=Et).—The adduct (III:R=Me; R'=Et) (6 g.) was heated with soda-lime (8 g.), as described before, when a liquid distillate was obtained. The distillate solidified on trituration with a little alcohol. On crystallisation from alcohol an unsharp melting substance was obtained. This was converted into the picrate in absolute alcoholic solution as deep orange needles, m.p. 176°. (Found: C, 65.3; H, 4.5. $C_{20}H_{22}O_7N_3$ requires C, 65.49; H, 4.48 per cent). The hydrocarbon was regenerated from the picrate and crystallised from alcohol as a pale yellow substance, m.p. 132°. (Found: C, 92.89; H, 7.0. $C_{22}H_{20}$ requires C, 92.95; H, 7.0 per cent).

11:12-Dihydro-10:13-diethyl-11:12-cyclopenteno-fluoranthene-11:12-dicarboxylic Anhydride (III:R=R'=Et).—The dimer of 2:5-diethyl-3:4-(1':8'-naphthylene)-cyclopentadienone (I:R=R'=Et) (10 g.) (Allen and Van Allan, *loc. cit.*) and Δ^1 -cyclopentene-1:2-dicarboxylic anhydride (7 g.) in xylene (30 c.c.) were heated, as described before. The adduct was washed with a little spirit and crystallised from benzene in cubes, m.p. 158°, yield 5.5 g. Freshly crystallised adduct was colorless but on keeping in air it acquired a pale pink colour. In most of the organic solvents it gave a light violet fluorescence. (Found: C, 81.07; H, 6.1. $C_{23}H_{22}O_2$ requires C, 81.09; H, 5.9 per cent).

10:13-Diethyl-11:12-cyclopenteno-fluoranthene (IV:R=R'=Et).—The adduct (III:R=R'=Et) (6 g.) was heated with soda-lime (8 g.) as, described before. A yellow sublimate (2.5 g.) was obtained. This was converted into picrate in absolute alcoholic solution as shining red needles, m.p. 174°. (Found: C, 65.8; H, 4.8. $C_{23}H_{22}O_7N_3$ requires C, 66.03; H, 4.74 per cent). The hydrocarbon was regenerated from the picrate and crystallised from alcohol in light yellow needles, m.p. 142°. (Found: C, 92.42; H, 7.42. $C_{23}H_{22}$ requires C, 92.61; H, 7.38 per cent).

2 : 5-Di-*p*-tolyl-3 : 4-(1' : 8'-naphthylene)-cyclopentadienone (I: R=R'=p-tol).—Acenaphthenequinone (9 g.) and *sym*-di-*p*-tolylacetone (15 g.) in ethyl alcohol (75 c.c.) were heated on a water-bath with alcoholic potash (2 c.c., 1:4). After half an hour the product separated in shining dark violet crystals. It was washed with spirit and crystallised from toluene, m.p. 225°, yield 6 g. (Found: C, 90.37; H, 5.49. C₂₂H₂₀O requires C, 90.62; H, 5.2 per cent).

11 : 12-Dihydro-10 : 13-di-*p*-tolyl-11 : 12-cyclopentenofluoranthene-11 : 12-dicarboxylic Anhydride (III: R=R'=p-tol).—2 : 5-Di-*p*-tolyl-3 : 4-(1' : 8'-naphthylene)-cyclopentadienone (I: R=R'=p-tol) (5 g.) and the anhydride of Δ^1 -cyclopentene-1 : 2-dicarboxylic acid (2 g.) were refluxed in xylene (20 c.c.), as described before. The adduct was crystallised from a large volume of toluene in needles, m.p. 240° (decomp.), yield 1.8 g. (Found: C, 84.54; H, 5.21. C₂₂H₂₀O₂ requires C, 85.02; H, 5.26 per cent).

The expenses incurred in this investigation were met from a research grant sanctioned by the Government of West Bengal.

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Received May 10, 1955.